

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF POLYMORPHISMS OF SOME GENES, RELATED TO PLATELET FUNCTION OF HEMOSTASIS WITH ANTIPLATELET RESISTANCE

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Relevance. Platelet activation and aggregation play a key role in the development of ischemic events. Double antiplatelet therapy with aspirin and clopidogrel in patients with coronary heart disease significantly reduces the number of adverse ischemic events. In recent years, much attention has been paid in the literature to such a concept as resistance to antiplatelet drugs. According to a number of authors, the range of resistance to aspirin varies between 5-45%, and to clopidogrel – 4-30%.

The aim of the work is to determine the frequency and structure of genetic factors that determine an individual predisposition to the development of aspirin resistance in patients with coronary heart disease in the Uzbek population.

Materials and methods: The study was performed on the basis of the Department of Cardiology of the RSNPT and MR. The study included 60 Uzbek patients diagnosed with coronary heart disease (48 men, 12 women; average age 59.5 ± 8.3 years). The control group consisted of almost 30 healthy persons of Uzbek nationality, comparable in gender and age with the study group. Genetic studies were conducted to determine the polymorphism of Leu33Pro of the $\beta 3$ integrin gene (ITGB3), polymorphism - Thr145Met of the platelet glycoprotein 1b gene, α -subunit (GP1BA), C786T mutation of the nitric oxide synthase 3 gene (NOS3), platelet ADP receptor mutation (P2RY12, H1/H2); integrin alpha-2 gene (glycoprotein Platelet Ia/IIa) (ITGA2), C807T mutation.

The results of the study: In the control group, the frequency of the mutant allele according to the studied polymorphisms was 16.4% in the ITGB3 gene (Leu33Pro), 16.4% in the CP1BA gene (Thr145Met), 45.3% in the NOS3 gene (C786T), 25.7% in the H1/H2 gene (P2RY12), which is significantly lower than those frequencies in the study group (32.4%, 43.8%, 61.6% and 38.2%, respectively, $p < 0.05$). The exception was the C807T (ITGA2) gene, where the differences with the group of examined patients were insignificant. The analysis of the frequency of polymorphisms revealed significant frequency exceedances of mutant ITGB3, CP1BA, NOS3 alleles in homozygous form ($OR = 1.29$; $= 1.94$;

=2.25, respectively, $p < 0.001$) in patients with antiplatelet resistance. The frequencies of polymorphisms of the H1/H2 gene differed to a lesser extent ($OR = 1.17$, $p = 0.01$) and there were no differences in the ITGA2 gene. A significant dependence of the fibrinogen content in the blood took place only on (and the GP1BA_Thr145Met genotype ($p = 0.030$).

Conclusions: The development of antiplatelet resistance in patients with coronary heart disease in the Uzbek population is associated with the presence of mutations ITGB3_Leu33Pro, GP1BA_Thr145Met, NOS3_C786T and P2RY12_H1H2. The greatest differences in the frequency of polymorphisms were determined for the Thr145Met mutation in the GP1BA gene.

